

AIM OF LINGUISTIC TYPOLOGY AND DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO THE SUBJECT

Karimova Umida
Istamova Shohista

Teachers of the department of English History and Grammar
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Ida Nyoman Tri Darma Putra

Teacher of STP Mataram (Mataram Tourism College)

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Annotation. Every language is like a one-of-a-kind species. It captures unique conceptualizations of the world and has its own ways of constructing words, phrases and sentences for communicating ideas. As we compare the words and structures of various languages, we come to a greater understanding of the world we live in. Apart from simply understanding the intricacies of world languages, this knowledge can be applied to improving communication between people, contributing to translation activities, assisting in literacy efforts, and treating speech disorders. And, of course, linguistics training is also valuable for studying and learning languages.

Key words: Typology, approaches, structure, ability, society, changes, languages, facts, differences, importance.

Introduction

Linguistic typology compares languages to learn how different languages are, to see how far these differences may go, and to find out what generalizations can be made regarding cross-linguistic variation. As languages vary at all levels, linguistic typology deals with all levels of language structure, including phonology, morphology, syntax, and semantics. Most linguistic disciplines have cross-linguistic comparison in the background, if not as their main method or object of inquiry. Even isolated descriptive traditions of individual languages, such as traditional descriptions of English, German, Russian, etc., are not free from cross-linguistic assumptions. Although rarely referring to them directly, they are all based on ideas about the structure of human language (often projected from Latin grammars), implicitly suggesting parallels between different languages. Yet these approaches are not typological, because they focus on one language, even when they borrow metalanguage applied to a different linguistic system.

Linguistic typology is a subfield of linguistics that studies and classifies languages according to their structural features. Its aim is to describe and explain the structural diversity of the world's languages. It includes three

subdisciplines: qualitative typology, which deals with the issue of comparing languages and within-language variance, quantitative typology, which deals with the distribution of structural patterns in the world's languages, and theoretical typology, which explains these distributions.

The words of any language are characterized by their ability to express definite notions existing in this society, thus changing their forms. Most of the notions existing in the society have common peculiarities, i.e. they have universal features. Among the linguistic categories which can be traced in most world languages we can see the categories which display typologically general feature but can be expressed in different ways. Studying these linguistic facts, identifying their similarities and differences is of much importance for the man of letters, especially for the graduates of the language faculties of universities, who are going to become English teachers and interpreters in the future. For example, the following linguistic notions as case, gender, person, tense voice, possession and etc. are of general feature for the comparing languages, but they may be expressed by typologically different means of the language.

The word typology consists of two Greek morphemes:

- a) typos means type and
- b) logos means science.

Typology is a branch of linguistics which is typical to all sciences without any exception. In this respect their typological method is not limited with the sphere of one science. It has a universal rise. So typology may be divided into:

1. Non-linguistic and
2. Linguistic typology

Non-linguistic typology is the subject matter of the sciences except linguistics.

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LINGUISTIC TYPOLOGY, also language typology, typology of language is a field of linguistics that studies and classifies languages according to their structural features. The classification of human languages into different types on the basis of shared properties which are not due to common origin or

geographical contact. Linguistic typology therefore complements the long-established tradition of genetic classification, in which languages are assigned to a family on the basis of their presumed historical origin. The criteria used for dividing languages into types depend to some extent on the purpose of the classification, since a typology based on sound structure does not necessarily correlate with one based on word order. The most common classificatory criteria are morphological (word structure), syntactic (word order), and phonological (sound patterns). Linguistic typology is an attempt to achieve this objective through a systematic analysis of language diversity.

Linguistic typology assumes that structures of different languages may be compared. Although this assumption seems to follow from the fact that the cognitive and social functions covered by various languages are roughly the same, answering specific questions about what is to be compared might be problematic. Typological comparison is based on the fact that linguistic signs (words, constructions, etc.) from different languages can be used in similar or identical situations. However, the position of a category in the system of a language, being at least partly independent of the real world, is an important factor which is or should be always kept in mind.

Conclusion

The classification of human languages into different types on the basis of shared properties which are not due to common origin or geographical contact. Its aim is to describe and explain the common properties and the structural diversity of the world's languages. Simply speaking, the study of universals is concerned with what human languages have in common, while the study of typology deals with ways in which languages differ from each other.

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